

1. Why we seek information?

Anna is on a hunger hunt! She wanted to try a new restaurant, but was not sure where to go. She searched it on Google and read the reviews of some places. She found out that an Italian joint has 4.5 stars. But she wanted more opinions for validation so she posted on Facebook. Britney informed her about a new sushi spot downtown, high on quality offering handsome combos within budget.

Anna's information-seeking journey was complete:

1. She recognized her need of finding a restaurant
2. She searched it online.
3. Consulted options and reviews.
4. Asked for recommendations through Facebook.

By using multiple sources (Google, Facebook) and by employing several search strategies (searching, browsing and asking) she made her decision relying on social recommendation. To move from uncertainty to certainty and to reduce entropy we need information. We need it for our survival and our enlightenment as well. To satisfy our conscious and unconscious need we need information. This need can be various ranging from physiological motives, social motives, for confirming already existing knowledge, to understand and examine existing knowledge etc. For example, Anna was driven by a physiological motive of hunger and later she confirmed from Britney regarding the better available option. Information seeking behaviour refers to the way people search for and applies the knowledge in their daily life to achieve some goal.

2. Why to understand information seeking behaviour?

Information seeking behaviour had its origin during the times when the production of scientific literature increased after the post-war period. The Royal Society Scientific Information Conference paved the beginning in the study of information seeking behaviour and later Library Science incorporated and taught it. Several models came out in existence like Wilson's Model of Information seeking behaviour (1981), his second model in 1994, Dervin's Sense-Making model, Ellis's model, Kuhlthaus's model, Leckie's model etc. There is a need to understand user's behaviour especially in the context of Library Science because libraries acquire, process and disseminate information and end-user satisfaction is their ultimate goal. As a user-oriented discipline, user's need, behaviour, perception need to be analysed to develop more fruitful methods and methodologies from time to time. Also, with the advent of information and communication technologies, the digital world has changed human information behaviour. Now the systems are getting accustomed to the user's choice and preferences on the basis of their search habits. In the current scenario, these behaviours have to be traced and accordingly the systems need to be upgraded to achieve the five proposed laws of Library Science-

- Books are for use
- Every Reader His/Her Book
- Every Book Its Reader
- Save the Time of the Reader
- Library is a Growing Organism

3. Everyday Life Information Seeking

Information seeking can be discussed in two major contexts: job-related and nonwork. When we talk about everyday life information seeking, it falls into the category of nonwork. ELIS studies talk about how people attain their information needs in various walks of life. During the early years of study, the concept of citizen information needs and seeking were associated with the information seeking which was happening outside work tasks. The approach was narrower because it referred to people's role in the society as voters or some kind of participants. Nonwork information seeking was considered to be less significant because it was not associated with daily works. But job-related and nonwork information seeking does overlap in daily situations- a person asking about computer courses can satisfy both his hobbies and professional needs. ELIS primarily refers to the acquisition of information through with people orient themselves in daily life which may not necessarily connect itself with the performance of professional tasks. On one level, it may refer to seeking of problem-centred information and on the other level simply for orienting information for monitoring everyday events.

The History

In the early 1970s, surveys were launched in the United States to study ordinary people's information needs and seeking. It was the first attempt of studying the conceptual and methodological aspects of ELIS. Marcia Bates came up with the concept of life information in 1974. It was followed by Brenda Dervin who created contemporary approaches of traditional ELIS survey research setting. ELIS studies have also identified popular information sources and channels. A telephone survey was conducted in New England in 1979 which showed that people preferred strongly the human sources in ELIS for problem solving. A recent study associated with environmental activists showed that they prefer mostly newspaper, Internet and television for seeking information. Overall, people prefer familiar sources which have functioned successfully in the past.

Elis in the context of Way of Life by Savolainen

“Way of life” as defined by Savolainen refers to “order of things”, based on individual's choices. “Things” stands for the different daily life activities that an individual undergoes related to jobs, household chores, hobbies etc. “Order” refers to the structure or how people cognitively give preference and organize these activities. There are three central issues here- structure of time budget, models of consumption of goods and services and nature of hobbies. Structure of time budget is proportion of time spent on work (job), nonwork (other necessary activities) and leisure time (recreation). Models of consumption indicates the money spent on the acquisition of goods and services. Nature of hobbies deals with what people find interest in, that is the substance of the way of life. When individuals make meaningful order of things that is known as mastery of life reflecting on the coherence of these everyday life tasks. It is a general preparedness to approach life problems in logical manner. Some of these life tasks as mentioned by Hektor may be generic (common to most people) or specific (arises as a result of one's life situation and choice). Mastery of life can be both passive and active. It is passive when people are satisfied to see everything happening as per their expectations. It becomes active when this order of things is shaken and problem solving is required. An important part of this mastery of life is information seeking. It eliminates the dissonance between how

things are at this moment and how it is expected to be. Without dissonance things go on routinely and information seeking becomes passive. With dissonance restoration of the disturbed order is required and here actively seeking information becomes essential. Savolainen utilized this model in a study conducted in Finland. Two groups were studied: teachers and industrial workers. The different ways of life of these two groups directs the information seeking in certain manner. Teachers were interested in seeking facts and light entertainment from various media. They were not interested in politics. Workers preferred documentaries and other serious programs. This shows that personal interest, professional interest and current life scenario (way of life) does affect their information seeking behaviour and also regarding how they use media. Theoretical framework and models of ELIS is low because there are smaller number of researchers who are active in this field. ELIS constitute the models of information seeking behaviour. Among the major ELIS models Sense-Making approach, the Small World Theory, ELIS in the context of way of life by Savolainen, Information Search Process are the renowned ones. One of the most influential researchers of ELIS since early 1970s is Brenda Dervin. Our main focus is on her Sense-Making approach which is a new viewpoint to ELIS and has significantly contributed to ELIS research.

2. Tracing the beginning of Sense-Making

Brenda Dervin, a stalwart of information and communication science was the chair of the Department of Communication at The Ohio State University. She did her Ph.D in communication research from Michigan State University after completing her Bachelors degree in journalism and home economics. She was awarded a doctorate in Political Science and in 2006, she received the Research in Information Science Award. Her conversations with Richard Carter paved the way of Sense-Making Methodology. In this section we will be talking about the basis of this renowned methodology:

“The communication field I entered was one bifurcated as it essentially remains to-day between polarized approaches-quantitative versus qualitative, administrative versus critical, and theory-driven versus applied and practical” (Dervin, Foreman-Warnet with Lauterbach, 2003).

Brenda Dervin initially talks about two kinds of theories- Substantive and Metatheories. The former deals with the systematic observation of any phenomena (quantitative approach) and the latter talks about the assumptions established regarding the phenomenon and how to study it. (qualitative approach). Both of these ideas are extremes in their own way, thus limiting the world within their own perspectives. A bridge or in-betweenness between these two extremes was drawn by creating a theory of methodology and Sense-making belongs to this third type. Even if sense-making methodology bridges the gap between two dominant ideas which are opposites, it is not doing away with the opposites. The differences are celebrated where Dervin mentions that people have their unique visions regarding the world which essentially can be different from the others. The difference in their perspectives celebrates their uniqueness. There is absolutely no need to resolve these differences and we all should be tolerant to support others visions. This schizophrenic quest of the in-betweenness lies at the heart of Dervin’s model.

3. Defying some past logic

The reason for Sense-making to become a ground making methodology was the fact that it challenged many assumptions with respect to communication. Instead of placing the users at the heart of the information system, the systems were built upon preconceived ideas or stereotypes.

Mr Squiggly's Computer Conundrum

Mr. Squiggly's computer had crashed. Desperate for a fix, he visited TechHub, a local repair shop.

Expert Eric examined the device muttering, "Your GPU's overheating due to a malfunctioning thermal paste, causing BSODs and CRC errors".

Mr. Squiggly's eyes widened in confusion "Huh? Is that good or bad?" He felt lost.

Eric nodded sympathetically- "Don't worry sir. It's fixable".

Squiggly pondered- "How can ordinary people like me keep up with expert's jargon? Is it possible for non-experts to grasp these complex concepts?". He walked away feeling a bit frustrated but determined to learn.

Mr. Squiggly faced the problem at the computer store because libraries and other organizations expect us to follow their prescribed norm. As a system we expect the audience (bucket heads) waiting to be filled. They expect users to know their vocabulary and terms. It was assumed that information is a brick which should be transmitted from the source to the receiver. The idea was we will only receive accurate information from others and we are to pass information accurately to others to communicate. In contrast, sense-making sees information as constructed internally to address the gaps rather than information which is out there waiting to be transmitted.

The information habit

Eric believed Squiggly to understand technical jargon is because the information systems are designed with the assumption that the recipient have the 'information habits'- they will come, they will receive information via a hypodermic needle and they will understand. Now receivers who can't figure out what is being said will be thought of deficient or disinterested. Therefore, the approach was system oriented not user oriented. On the other hand, the users are just getting a collision of words which are difficult for them to make meaning of.

Predicting a need in advance

The information systems are predicting the user's static information requirements in advance. When it is predicting people, it is predicting what the state owns. It will predict low-income behaviour when low-income behaviour is constrained by the state. Therefore, Habitual behaviour can be predicted when the state constrains it. But can Communicative behaviour be

predicted? What happens if a user does not behave according to the system? There are two types of theories describing why our efforts to communicate fail-

Theory 1 says that the recipients of information are leaky bucket heads. After a certain point they fail to retain the information and thus information leaks.

Theory 2 is the recalcitrant bucket where the recipient refuses to the system and does not behave the way the system wants. His need cannot be predicted.

In the light of the second theory, Dervin here creates a figure representing an average person- Mr. Squiggly. Squiggly implies that the person is both ordered and disordered. Taking a stand between these polarities Dervin stands in between the modern (assuming humans to be rational) and post-modern (assuming humans to be decentred) approach. The system needs to understand the users. The users when approaching the systems are meddling into the unknown and if the systems impose their terminologies, concepts upon the users it will lead to gap. Sensemaking methodology brackets all the nouns and puts a set of verbing questions as alternatives. We have to stop talking to people in the nouns of our world and allow people to put their world's noun on our planes, to understand or make sense of their conditions.

Dervin's Squiggly (Dervin, 2011)

The information brick

Seeing people as they have the information habit

4. Making sense of the Sense-Making

Dervin's Sense-making theory (1983) apart from being a model of information-seeking behaviour is a set of assumptions, a methodological approach which is designed to make sense of the reality which is both chaotic and ordered. Dervin describes her position as post-critical. Her Sense-making methodology invokes Foucault, Gramsci, Friere and Bordieu. The model's philosophical origin can be traced to the Greek philosophers and later, Hegel.

The Sense-making approach is based on Dervin's Situation-Gap theory. Users go through different phases in making sense of the world. The first phase is called Situation which builds the context of information need. People find a gap between what they understand and what they need to know to make order of the current situation (between the contextual situation and desired situation). Outcome arrives as the result of the process and a Bridge closes the gap between the situation and the outcome. Therefore, the four constructs introduced by Dervin are Situation, Gap, Bridge and Outcome. The central metaphor of sense making remains time, space, gap, situations, bridge and outcome where we travel through time and space, encounter gaps, build bridges across the gaps, analysing outcomes and going on. Each new movement in time and space requires us to take another step of gap-bridging regardless of the fact that whether that step is taken as habitual or unconscious; invented or planned. Information seeking behaviour can be clearly explained through this model:

A person is suffering from asthma (situation) but is unaware of how to cure the ailment (gap). He finds information from various sources like doctors, friends, mass media etc (bridge) to enable himself to cope up with it and return to a healthy lifestyle (outcome).

Dervin's situation-gap theory (Dervin, c1999)

From its inception days Sense making has been trying out to find what users think, want and dream. The theory assumes that we live in a world of gaps. This is the reality that changes across time and place. Our differences fill up the human society and the self is sometimes centered, sometimes muddled but always getting structured. Sense making and Sense unmaking views that Knowledge as a verb is an activity which is embedded in time and space. Another aspect of Sense making says that there is a close connection between how we view a situation and what sense we make out of the situation (methodological analysis). Some realisations from studying this model are given below:

1. People enact the situation they face in their narratives. As they speak and build narrative accounts it enables them to organize their thought and control or predict events.
2. Retrospection helps in sensemaking.
3. Sense making is an ongoing process where individuals simultaneously shape and react to the situations they encounter.
4. People extract cues from their context which helps them to link ideas to broader meanings of life.
5. Human beings are moving through time and space, embedded in history, facing the present reality and predicting future goals. Though they are anchored in material conditions, their inner and outer realms of existence are inseparable.
6. Humans are constantly becoming and unbecoming. The quest of the systems to predict a static information need of an user is futile.
7. Culture and community cannot solve communication problems because of the diversity existing within this group than between these groups.
8. Reality is subjected to changes and is always filled with gaps
9. Information becomes meaningful when it is translated into reality based on intelligence and wisdom.
10. In user studies users are placed at different boxes for the purpose of dividing them- Demography (age, ethnicity, education etc), Capabilities (literacy, completeness etc) Traits (Personality), cognitive or emotive styles (complexity), lifestyles (hobbies,

interests), domain (engineer, scientist), task (writing a paper), channel (message packages), institution (private, public). Communicative behaviour cannot be predicted through them because their lies more differences within these boxes than between these boxes.

5. Application of Dervin's model in Library Science

Dervin's Sense Making methodology has been applied to a reference interview technique called Neutral questioning. This technique allows the interviewee to express his information need freely making the interviewer (the reference librarian) to be in control of the conversation. Neutral questioning was introduced to librarians through educational workshops. In 1981, Dervin started teaching Neutral-Questioning in "Turning Public Libraries Around". The University of Western Ontario started workshops on the same in 1982 which was followed by Canadian Library Association in a series of workshops designed by Dewdney and Catherine Ross.

In the process of query negotiation, the librarian plays an intermediary role between the system and the user. The librarian interviews the user to determine his need and the process takes place through dialogic conversation. Due to the lack of a theoretical model for teaching interview techniques of reference interview there was no systematic approach formulated previously. The existing traditional and alternative approaches never focused on the nature of information and information-seeking behaviour. The term 'Neutral questioning' was used in 1981 by Dervin to describe some communication techniques taught in the workshops for practicing librarians. Here the librarian understands the query from the user's point of view. There are three kinds of questions that a reference librarian uses- Closed question, Open question and Neutral questions. Closed questions when asked to the users limit their responses to yes or no. Whether the question asked is relevant to the user's context is not searched. They involve a judgement already predicted by the librarian and they try to match the user to the familiar parts of the system. So, this is system-centric.

Open questions allows users to freely express their need and unlike closed system doesnot expose the users to narrow range of choices. They move from system-oriented to user-oriented approach and in the process the conversations which are generated can be both relevant and irrelevant to the interview.

Neutral questions are very much like open questions; the only difference is that it always keeps in mind the relevant context. Here librarian learns from the user the underlying situation, the gaps faced and the outcome or the uses thereby keeping the three elements of the Sense-Making model intact. In this way, the librarians can control the interview by only moving along the jurisdiction of relevancy. Users also exercise control by avoiding premature diagnosis of the librarian and they describe their wants only in the dimension they want. This approach therefore is also user-oriented. An example is given below-

Case 1: Closed Question

Librarian -Are you interested in paper making industry?

User-Yes/No

Case 2: Open Question

Librarian- What details do you want?

User- I want information on the processing from raw materials to finished products.

Case 3: Neutral Questions

Librarian- On which aspect do you want your information? Selection of raw materials, pulping process, stock preparation, sheet formation, finishing, paper testing and quality control are some probable areas of research.

User- I am interested in the pulping process to sheet formation.

According to sense-making communication strategies are situationally based. None of the strategies are nullifying the others. All of them have different consequences and should be selected depending upon the user's intention. Closed, open and neutral questions are all appropriate in different situations.

Some of the librarians after practicing neutral questions pointed out some difficulties. They found it odd. They preferred such communications in extreme cases. The reason for their resistance was the fact that this approach challenged the traditional way of thinking of the librarians. However, experienced librarians have also confirmed that this approach saves time because they don't have to ponder around their own assumptions of user's need and could enter into the actual process. Despite of these differences in the responses, Neutral Questioning remains effective particularly in specialized setting, scientific and technical centres, referral centres etc.

6. A case study in the field of Health Communication.

In the Journal of Administrative Science, two researchers Ismail Sualman and Rosni Jaafar presented an application of the Sense making model which shows that this model has universal approaches in fields other than Library Science as well. In the following experiment Focus group discussions were used for the purpose of data collection on the health conditions of the individuals in Malaysia. Health communication issues have not been studied in qualitative manner till now and many studies usually focus on the use and effects of media neglecting audience's interaction with the media. Sampling technique is used based on unique location, target audience, time and event to make the study fruitful. Individuals above 30 years were selected who had Secondary education and were employed. They were concerned about their health being exposed to the Healthy Life Style campaign (1990). The study dealt mainly with the following-

- To study individual's personal experience related to healthcare.
- To study the barriers often faced.
- To identify the sources providing health information.
- To investigate their needs, their information seeking behaviour and their utilization of knowledge.

About the Informants

Four focus groups were created-

Group 1: 4 males 4 females from Malay ethnic group. Age- 30-53 years. Profession- Government and private staff.

Group 2: 4 female Malays and 4 Chinese Malays. Age- 30-45 years. Profession- Businesswomen.

Group 3: 3 Malay housewives, 3 Indian housewives, 4 retired Malay men. Age- above 50 years. Profession- Retired.

Group 4: 4 Chinese men, 2 Indian men and 3 Malay men. Age- 30-45 years. Profession- Support staff in government and private sectors.

Predicting the Information need (Situation)

The informants were suffering from certain health problems which builds their context of situation. They need certain information to overcome their current state. They need information for the following:

- To cure their ailment,
- To prevent the disease from further spreading into their community,
- To predict their symptoms or to know which stage they are in
- Medicine needed
- Available treatment and alternative treatment
- Cause of the illness
- Who can cure them and case studies of people suffering the same disease
- Preventive measures

Bridging the Gap

From interviewing the focus groups, the researchers came to know that to move from contextual situation to desired situation that is to bridge the Gap, these informants consulted government doctors, specialists, private doctors, Internet, mass media, their local witch doctors and people who had suffered from the illness in the past to know more about their actual situations. The informants received some recommendations from these sources.

In this context, Barriers are often encountered in information seeking. For high income group surfing the Internet, consulting a doctor is possible but coming to the low-income group these choices are problematic. Low-income group are most likely to rely on local doctors, friends and families due to financial problems. Also, the informants face time constraints due to their jobs. These constraints vary from person to person due to the different types of occupation they are involved in.

Outcome

This is the stage when the informants utilized their information. They were successful in controlling their illness. It helped them to cure their stress, uncertainty and the fear of the disease. They monitored their illnesses carefully preventing it to worsen further and also to

stop their spreading. Patients in the preliminary stages became more vigilant and their risk factor of death vanished.

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